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ENERGY AND RESOURCE SAVING RESEARCH OF RESIDENTIAL BUILDINGS

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Abstract: This study is devoted to the theme "Research on Energy and Resource Efficiency in Residential Buildings" and explores the importance of energy and resource conservation. In the context of global warming and limited energy resources, improving energy efficiency in residential buildings, ensuring the well-being of the population, and maintaining ecological stability are urgent issues. The research process considers modern technologies for enhancing energy efficiency, insulation materials, smart systems, and lighting methods.

Key words: energy, construction, resource, building materials, efficiency, economics, competition, production, monitoring, management, system, insulation.

Today, issues of saving energy and resources are important on a global scale. For developing countries like Uzbekistan, this issue is related to the increase in population and the need to reduce energy consumption. Residential buildings are the main residences of the population, and their level of energy efficiency and resource use plays an important role in the sustainable development of society. [6]

Energy efficiency is the process of increasing the efficiency of the use of energy resources, while maintaining comfort and quality. The main goal of this process is to reduce energy consumption, reduce costs and greatly reduce the environmental impact. [1]

There are several key aspects of improving energy efficiency in residential buildings. Building insulation can significantly reduce energy consumption. Building insulation using

new materials, such as mineral fiber or polystyrene, reduces heat loss. As an example, medium- and high-rise buildings located in the cities and districts of Khorezm region are often not insulated, which leads to a high loss of energy consumption.[2]

Insulation materials play an important role in improving energy efficiency. Modern insulation materials include: Mineral fiber is a material that is effective in retaining heat and helps to keep the indoor environment of the building in a comfortable condition. Mineral fiber is an insulation material made mainly from stone or glass fibers. It is effective in heat, sound and fire protection and is used in many construction industries. Polystyrene is highly efficient in saving energy, but its environmental impact should also be taken into account. (PS) Thermoplastic material that is often used as insulation. It is often available in solid and transparent form. [3,5]

Modern heating and cooling systems, such as air conditioners and panel heaters, are designed to improve energy efficiency. Technologies are

updated every year to improve their efficiency. Saving resources, especially water and electricity, is a difficult issue. The following methods can be used in residential buildings. Energy savings can be achieved with the help of LED lighting systems and energy-saving appliances. Energy-saving equipment should be installed and used in all buildings of our Republic. Energy consumption can be controlled and managed with the help of smart home systems. These systems effectively manage energy consumption. Sensors monitor temperature, lighting, energy consumption in the home and can optimize energy consumption. [4]

Energy conservation and efficient use of resources are of social importance. This helps to improve the health of the population and improve the quality of life. Economical systems and energy efficiency help clean the air, which has a positive effect on public health.

Saving energy and efficient use of resources will bring economic benefits. Investments in energy-saving technologies help increase economic

benefits and reduce costs. After investments in energy-saving systems are made, economic efficiency can be analyzed by calculating payback periods. Real-time monitoring systems allow monitoring energy consumption in the building. With these systems, energy consumption can be controlled and optimized. Monitoring systems allow you to monitor energy consumption inside the building, get accurate information and analyze it in real time to reduce energy consumption.

Conclusions and suggestions.

Research on energy and resource efficiency of residential buildings is necessary to make them more efficient and sustainable. With the help of modern technologies and evaluation methods, it is possible to reduce energy consumption and optimize the use of resources. This not only ensures ecological stability, but also improves the well-being of the population.

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